

Data-driven Degradation-Aware Model Predictive Control for Power Electronics

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Abstract—With the development of artificial intelligence, the control strategies for critical power devices has a diversity such that more reliability solution can be guaranteed in diversity complicated working condition. LC-inverter is known as one of the most applied power conversion equipment nowadays due to the significantly increasing demand for more electrical transportation and multiple renewable energy source generation. To address the challenge of developing a degradation-aware control strategy, this paper intend to incorporate a novel degradation to the finite-set model predictive control for the LC inverter.

Index Terms—Artificial intelligence, model predictive control, degradation, inverter, power MOSFET

I. INTRODUCTION

Along with rapid evolution of the renewable energy source (RES) and increased electrical transportation, power electronic inverters intend to act as a critical role in a multitude of applications. These inverters are essential for converting DC power to AC power with high efficiency and reliability. However, the performance and longevity of LC inverters are often challenged by component degradation over time, which can lead to reduced efficiency, increased harmonic distortion, and potential failure.

Conventional control strategies for inverters mainly focus on the stability, power balancing and harmonic analysis, nevertheless, has paid less attention to the mitigation of the component's for example SiC MOSFET degradation. This oversight can result in underlying gradually suppressed performance and unexpected downtime, impacting the overall system stability, operation and maintenance costs. To address these challenges, degradation-aware or reliability-oriented control strategies as a robust solution, integrating the principles of model predictive control with real-time degradation monitoring. Model Predictive Control (MPC) has been known as a prominent control strategy that utilizes a dynamic model of the system to predict future behavior and optimize control actions accordingly. By incorporating degradation awareness into this framework, DAMPC dynamically adjusts its control strategy based on the real-

time health state of the inverter components. This approach not only enhances performance but also extends the lifespan of the inverter by mitigating the effects of degradation. Furthermore, Artificial intelligence(AI) has been significantly increasing utilized in different perspective of power electronic applications [1], [2], particularly enhancing controlling and maintenance. Traditionally a optimal control problem can be robustly solved out by dynamic programming and other similar mathematical methods, subsequently, nowadays can be intensively handled by advance data-driven techniques, which specifically in many research papers refers to the reinforcement learning(RL)-based development [3]–[5].

In this paper, we will discuss and evaluate a data-driven degradation assessment to continuously monitor key indicators of component health, in this case, which stands for the on-state resistance aging and thermal stress on semiconductor devices. By integrating these degradation models into the predictive control algorithm, the control strategy can proactively adjust operating parameters to minimize stress and delay degradation effects. This real-time adaptation ensures that the inverter operates within safe margins, maintaining high efficiency and power quality despite the aging of components.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

As a great concern of reliability of operation, incorporating the degradation assessment into the predictive control has been attracted scholar's attention, assisted by AI-driven decision making strategies. The impact of deterioration to the system operation can be traced back to the control strategy that lead to unexpected stress or other abnormal circumstance. In this case, with appropriate modelling of the degradation and system behaviour of the control plant, the underlying deterioration may be discerned via the monitored input and output signal by applying data-driven techniques. As [6] stated: "A model of behaviour is said to be degradation-dependent when it is possible to monitor and quantify the degradation (usually by means of measurements of the input and output of the system)". Typically, a degradation dependent modelling associated with the condition monitoring (CM) data from the controlled system tends to incorporate the quantification of the degradation impact $h(d(\cdot))$, state equation $\dot{x}(t) = A(t)x(t) + B(t)u(t)$,

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measurement equation $y(t) = C(t)x(t) + D(t)u(t)$, and timestamp t :

$$\dot{x}_D(t) = f(t, x_D(t), u_D(t), h(d)) \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{y}_D(t) = g(x_D(t), u_D(t), h(d)) \quad (2)$$

Two paradigm are taken into account to embed the degradation model into the system behaviour identification. Firstly, the degradation modelling $h(d)$ can be constituted by stochastic factors which quantified by fixed time-dependent value. The degradation model should be assumed to be independent of the control action.

$$h(d) = h(d(t)) \quad (3)$$

Additionally, the degradation model should involve the time-dependent system state and control action:

$$h(d) = h(d(d, v, x(t), u(t), y(t))) \quad (4)$$

Beyond obtaining the CM dataset from the sensor network, optimization algorithms such as genetic algorithm(GA) can be applied to find out the parameters of the degradation modeling. One of the most applied degradation model of power MOSFET thermal-sensitive electrical parameter (TSEP) was exponential function [7]–[10]:

$$D(t) = a(e^{bt} - 1) \quad (5)$$

Once the comprehensive modelling is identified, the optimal management of device operation can be revised along with real-time monitoring of the system. Specifically, degradation can be mitigated by optimal control so that the estimated remaining useful life(RUL) can be closer to the expected maintenance schedule [11].

From the perspective of controlling a power electronic system, the decision making usually stand for limiting or compensating output power by manipulating the switching-based actuator of the semiconductor. Gate control optimization has been extensively studied in recent years to mitigate the switching loss, delay and distortion under the circumstance of high-temperature degradation [12]–[14]. A study has [15] stated that the optimization of parallel operation of SiC MOSFET could be considered as a decision-making problem, where reinforcement learning(RL) presents ultra-performance on defining the action. For example, the difference between the temperature and current with their set point can be used to construct the reward function, subsequently, leading to the optimal gate driver voltage setting. Reliability-oriented control has been discussed in [16] where the author incorporated the degradation of the power MOSFET which based on the exponential lifetime mathematical modeling and Miner's rule. Notably, the author enhanced the reliability of a droop control for the inverter that deployed to a AC microgrid by tuning the coefficient of the droop amount:

$$m_p = m_{p0}[\alpha + (1 - \alpha)\beta_m^\lambda] \quad (6)$$

Specifically, they stated that when the output power of the inverter greater than the set point, the accumulated damage D

should be greater than the reference of accumulated damage, result in the weighted factor β_m^λ located in the range between 0 and 1. Eventually, the reliability-oriented control strategy will limit the output power by suppressing the duty ratio so that the thermal stress of power MOSFET will be mitigated.

Above all, motivated by the idea of taking advantage of strong computation capability of AI techniques to enhance the reliability of a power MOSFET-based power conversion devices, we address the following challenges in this study:

- 1) We propose a degradation assessment method that incorporates the estimation of accumulated deterioration accompanied with intrinsic degradation. Each of them is described by a linear and a non-linear function separately. We applied classic Bayesian regression and a meta-heuristic algorithm to optimize the parameter which construct an effective degradation model for the power MOSFET on-state resistance under different working condition.
- 2) Since predictive control can enhance the stability of the behaviour of power device by setting up a suitable prediction steps, intuitively this objective is well adapted to health estimation applications. Therefore, the second aim of this study is conducting an exploration that taking advantage of the thermal-sensitive degradation modelling. We deployed the model to the optimal control problem of a LC inverter to mitigate the over-thermal stress that raised by a high-frequency switching operation.

Fig. 1. The change of the #12 Device under test(DUT)'s on-state resistance with respect to the increasing working temperature,

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Thermal-sensitive degradation modeling

Typically, the objective of TSEP condition monitoring was set out to be the online identification of the critical static or dynamic condition that reflects the real-time health state of the MOSFET from the huge amount of data flow and historical dataset during common operation. The captured conditions can be directly selected, or indirectly derived as a generalized or specific precursor to be predicted by applying pre-trained online model-based or learning-based approaches. Intelligence

Fig. 2. Monitoring the on-state resistance versus aging experiment,

decision-making could be further formulated based on forming a state space of the monitored device. Namely, sufficient historical data and appropriate modelling of the physics entity are the premises for carrying out a prevention strategy. To assess the degradation level of a power MOSFET that deployed to a LC inverter which working under a high temperature circumstance, we involved 3 time-dependent factor for the modeling the impact of the changing rate of the temperature and underlying cumulative fatigue. On-state resistance is known as one of the most effective TSEP as it can significantly influence the performance of power conversion. The proposed degradation function of R_{dson} is described as:

equation can be transformed into:

$$D_R(t) = \rho(\theta(t))[D_{th}(T) + D_a(t, T)] \quad (8)$$

t denotes the timestamp and T denotes the temperature. The degradation that induced by increasing temperature is described as a linear function as figure illustrated:

$$D_{th}(T) = \epsilon_T T + b \quad (9)$$

As figure 2 shows, when the temperature stays in a stable range, the on-state resistance still increased gradually and finally lead to latch-up failure. To take into account such degradation pattern, the cumulative degradation with respect to the working temperature and corresponding working time period, in this case, is described as:

$$D_a(t, T) = \epsilon_A(T) \int_t^{t+\Delta T} \alpha_D (e^{\beta_D t} - 1) \quad (10)$$

Above all, the parameters set of the degradation model is:

$$(\rho, \epsilon_T, \epsilon_A(T), \alpha_D, \beta_D, b) \quad (11)$$

To construct the model, $D_{th}(T)$ should be fitted at first by utilizing the data which stands for the relationship between the temperature and R_{dson} . In this paper, we applied the Bayesian regression to fitting the linear function. The performance of the Bayesian linear function fitting depends on the parameter selection for the distribution of noise and regression coefficient. Thus, correspondingly, ϵ_T and b will be estimated based on the Bayesian inference, its procedure follows:

- 1) Setup a hyper-parameter combination $\theta = (\alpha_D, \beta_D)$ to establish the distribution for the coefficient and bia(noise) component:

$$b \sim N(0, \lambda^{-1}) \quad (12)$$

$$\epsilon_T \sim N(0, \varepsilon^{-1}) \quad (13)$$

- 2) Compute the likelihood for the estimated parameter, then obtain the sum of the likelihood on each sample:

$$P(Y|\theta) = N(Y, \epsilon_{T,\theta} X + b_\theta, \theta) \quad (14)$$

Fig. 3. The framework of proposed method to enhance the reliability of three-phase LC inverter with data-driven condition monitoring and decision making,

$$D_R(t) = h(t, D_{th}(T), D_a(t, T), \delta_{CL}(t)) \quad (7)$$

The closed-loop control demand $\delta(t)$, could be denoted by the duty ratio, or simply denoted by on and off state. Hence, this

- 3) Compute the posterior estimation based on the selected hyper-parameters:

$$P(\theta|X, Y) = P(Y|\theta)P(\theta) \quad (15)$$

The reason of applying Bayesian regression due to the motivation of distributing a probability for the estimation that can be further guided by a regularization in a different sampling period. As mentioned in [9], the hazard rate of the power MOSFET should consider the aging factor together with a time-varying covariance which denoted a regression coefficients. However, due to the limitation of the dataset, we are not going to evaluate this advance in the following content.

B. GA-driven precursor estimation

After obtaining the temperature-dependent degradation above, the genetic algorithm(GA) is utilized to find the optimal solution of the parameter set for the degradation modeling. Compare to the particle swarm optimization(PSO) and simulated annealing(SA), GA presents more robust computation without depending on a gradient calculation. Since the degradation of modern power MOSFET usually last for a long time, the disadvantage of expensive computation could be neglected in the industrial process. Inspired by the process of natural selection, the optimization procedure of GA follows few steps:

- 1) Initialize the population with encoding, which maps the solution to the encode space
- 2) Evaluate the fitness of each individual to justify their potential in the next round.
- 3) Iterate following step until the termination condition is met:
 - a) Choosing a suitable parents for generating the samples in the next generation
 - b) Construct the crossover strategy to define the next generation.
 - c) Apply mutation to the samples in the next generation.
 - d) Evaluate the fitness function.
 - e) Replace individuals in the population with offspring
- 4) Localize and return the optimal solution

The typical hyper-parameter of the GA is population size and crossover operation as they dominates the computation complexity and the search ability. In practice, in most of industrial application, meta-heuristic is also very sensitive to the setup of initial value and the boundary constraint. Thus, designing an optimization algorithm sometimes can be very expensive associated with huge amount of observation of the performance in terms of multiple setting. To solve the problem of finding the optimal parameter, the objective function of the GA is set as:

$$J = \sum_0^T (D_R(t) - \Delta R_{dson})^2 \quad (16)$$

Where the change of the on-state resistance which subject to a fixed working temperature T is described as:

$$\Delta R_{dson} = R_{dson,T}(\Delta t) - R_{dson,T}(0) \quad (17)$$

C. Finite-set Model Predictive Control for LC inverter

In this paper, a three-phase LC inverter FS-MPC control strategy [17], which has been proven to be a prominent method for the controlling, is applied to evaluate the feasibility of the proposed method. The topology of the inverter is showed in the figure 3 which switch operation is described as:

$$S = \frac{2}{3}(S_a + aS_b + a^2S_c) \quad (18)$$

The behaviour of the switching for a single power MOSFET only refers to the on and off state. Taking advantage of the Hence, the load voltage associates with the switching operation by:

$$v_{load} = SV_{dc} \quad (19)$$

Combining the cost function presented in [18] with the degradation mitigation decision-making, the cost function of the LC inverter optimal control is:

$$g = (v_{f\alpha}^* - v_{f\alpha})^2 + (v_{f\beta} - v_{f\beta}^*)^2 + J_d + J_{THD} + J_{sw} + J_D \quad (20)$$

The penalty of the degradation which induced by a continuous operation at a high temperature is added to the cost function designed by previous scholars. Assuming the temperature rising ΔT is monitored in a control horizon, it could be described as:

$$J_D = \omega_D \int_{t_0}^{t_0+t_h} (D_R(t_0 + \tau) - D_R(t_0))dt \quad (21)$$

ω_D denotes the weight of this component which should be selected manually or by applying artificial neural network. The integration of increased degradation in terms of the initial degradation level at the first time of the sampling period is tailored to mitigate the whole degradation, in a way of reducing switching operation, the penalty of which is controlled by the coefficient ω_{sw} . Once the degradation is observed, it will be adjusted to:

$$\omega_{sw,D} = \omega_{sw} + J_D \quad (22)$$

The prediction of $D_R(t_0 + \tau)$ at the last prediction step within the FS-MPC is based on the pre-trained aforementioned model with respect to temperature measurement.

IV. CASE STUDY

As mentioned in the first section, this paper address the challenge of developing a degradation-aware control strategy for inverter. Two steps will be presented in the experiment part. In the first step, the NASA dataset [7] was utilized to exploring the feasibility of the proposed method. The switching operation executed until reaching the pre-set certain level T_{max} , at a duty ratio of 40%, while the frequency was 1kHz and the amplitude of gate supply was 12V. Before presenting the explanation of experiment result, some problem should be mentioned as a promising for establishing a meaningful degradation dataset. The sampling time of the dataset is not consistent from the beginning to the end. Some of the sampling period was more than 10 seconds while the shortest one was less than 1 second. The measurement of the package

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF THE DEGRADATION MODEL PARAMETER OPTIMIZATION WITH GA

Function tolerance	Population size	Crossover Fraction	Elite Count	Best value of cost function
1e-4	2000	0.9	10	2179
1e-4	5000	0.9	10	2145
1e-6	2000	0.9	50	2145
1e-6	2000	0.9	200	2149

temperature presented huge amount of apparent abnormal value, as a result, few of the DUT can be utilized for a data-driven development. Hence, #8, #9, #11, #12 and #14 DUT were selected in the experiment. The drifting of the R_{dson} is showed in the figure which stand for a continuous operation. Apparently, the type of the power MOSFET and the working condition was the same, the changing rate of each one presented a totally different trend over their lifetime. In this section, we capture the drift of the parameter from the samples which working at a stable flange temperature was around 210 degree to carry out a analysis under a fixed working condition. According to the description [19], the samples from the aforementioned DUT at the fifth and sixth aging run can fulfill this requirement. The aging time for each of them was 240, 180, 180 minutes.

Fig. 4. The drift of on-state resistance at a fixed over-thermal stress,

A. Degradation assessment

As showed in figure 1, since the linear relationship between the ascending temperature with the changing of R_{dson} is very clear, thus in this paper the performance of the GA-based parameter optimization should be paid more attention to in this part. As table I illustrated, four hyper-parameters of the GA algorithm is compared in terms of the best value of the cost function. According to the experiment result On the other hand, according to figure 4, the estimation of the degradation is very sensitive to the change of temperature, the modelling

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE METRICS COMPARISON FOR THE PROPOSED DEGRADATION-AWARE CONTROL STRATEGY

Description	THD	f_{sw}
Without degradation	5.32%	5.81kHz
Degradation + without switching penalty	5.44%	5.67kHz
Degradation + with switching penalty	4.66%	5.17kHz

of which is linear function. When the temperature was fixed, the value increased very slowly in terms of time.

In addition, the upper boundary and lower boundary of the parameter was also a promising factor of an effective optimization, which were separately setup to $[1, 1, 0.0002]$ and $[0, 0, 0.000001]$. The limitation of β_D is one of the key point to obtaining the best solution in this case, as it dominated the differential of the exponential degradation function. The estimation was found to be very far away from the ground truth when it went over the upper boundary, meanwhile, it was nearly not possible for the GA searching a global solution.

B. Performance of the Degradation-aware FS-MPC

To evaluate the performance of proposed control strategy, we compared the metrics which quantifying the quality of the output voltage and switching operation loss. As table II demonstrated, three experiment was carried out, the best performance of which was obtained from the proposed control strategy. The total harmonic distortion (THD) was relatively lower than the other two setup, while the average switch frequency was much lower than the setup which without the proposed cost function. Thus, it's feasible to take advantage of degradation model to the control strategy for power device associated with effective condition monitoring for the critical TSEPs.

When a part of the R_{dson} upon the inverter start to drift, the three phase output will not be able to keep balance in a short time. As figure 5 showed, the above sub-figure stands for the inverter output voltage that controlled by the proposed method, while the other one stands for the waveform that only controller by the FS-MPC. After the occurrence of degradation, the voltage that controlled by the proposed method recover to the set-point much quicker than the other one. This can be due to the manipulated switching operation that can against the impact of such abnormal output.

V. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

This paper proposes a novel degradation-aware control strategy for inverter to enhance the lifetime performance

Fig. 5. The change of the on-state resistance with respect to the increasing working temperature,

and the reliability associated with a novel degradation modelling method. We utilized classic machine learning regression method and meta-heuristic algorithm to robustly find the most suitable parameters for the degradation modelling. As the result demonstrated, it's feasible and effective to apply the proposed method to improve the reliability and stability of inverter system.

In the future, we will develop a HIL experiment to evaluate the control algorithm in a real-world inverter system associated with a condition monitoring for the thermal stress. From the perspective of degradation modeling, we will explore an advanced aging modeling in terms of a comprehensive probability-based, which will be eventually applied to the decision making section in the optimal control on both side of the inverter.

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